

Synthesis and bioactivity of ternary mixed ligand complexes of copper(II) and zinc(II) with substituted pyrimidine

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Six new mixed ligand complexes of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with 5-substituted-2-dimethylamino-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine have been prepared. Their herbicidal, fungicidal and insecticidal activities have been evaluated. Complex, Cu(C₈H₁₃N₃O)₂Cl₂ (3) has 81.9% of herbicidal activity against barnyardgrass.

Pyrimidine compounds play a significant role in many biological systems¹. Many compounds of therapeutic importance contain the pyrimidine ring system. Pyrimidine derivatives, which are used as insecticides, herbicides and fungicides, exhibit good bioactivity and behavior in environment². On the other hand, the pyrimidine ring system has potential binding sites for metal ions. The information on the pyrimidine's coordinating properties is important in understanding the role of the metallic ions in biological system. Many drugs modify their pharmacological and toxicological properties in the form of metallic complexes³. Complexation of pesticides with metals has potential advantages including the enhancement of persistence, longer shelf life, reduction of mammalian toxicity and conversion of non-systemic to systemic pesticides^{4,5}.

In order to enhance the information on the coordination properties of pyrimidine ring we report herein the syntheses, characterizations and biological activities of new mixed ligand complexes of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with 5-substituted-2-dimethylamino-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidines.

Results and discussion

Elemental analyses indicate that reaction of 5-substituted-2-dimethylamino-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine (Fig. 1) with metal chloride (CuCl₂, ZnCl₂) afford complexes having the molecular formula ML₂Cl₂ (L : ligand, M : copper, zinc). The complexes are quite stable in air. The adduct complexes are fairly soluble in DMF and DMSO, but are almost insoluble in chloroform, benzene, methanol and ethanol. The complexes in DMF show molar conductance values in the range of 5–32

Fig. 1

Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ supporting their non-ionic character (Table 1).

Table 1. Analytical and conductance data of metal pyrimidine complexes*

Compd. no.	Ligand R	Compd.	Mol. cond. Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹
1	H	Cu(L ₁) ₂ Cl ₂	32
2	H	Zn(L ₁) ₂ Cl ₂	10
3	CH ₃	Cu(L ₂) ₂ Cl ₂	22
4	CH ₃	Zn(L ₂) ₂ Cl ₂	5.8
5	C ₃ H ₇	Zn(L ₃) ₂ Cl ₂	9.0
6	C ₄ H ₉	Zn(L ₄) ₂ Cl ₂	5.0

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

In the presence of nitrogen, [Zn(L₁)₂Cl₂] complex undergoes complete decomposition in three stages. The first stage between 200–280° is accompanied by a mass loss of 33.8% (calculated 34.6%) and corresponds to removal of one pyrimidine radical (L₁). The decomposition of the remaining part between 280–580° occurs in the

second stage and corresponds to removal of another pyrimidine radical (L_1) which has a weight loss of 36.4% (calculated 34.6%). In the last stage, decomposition of $ZnCl_2$ to Zn occurs in the temperature range 580–680°.

The general decomposition scheme of the complexes **1-6** can be summarized in the following manner (Fig. 2). The results of DTA-TG analyses also support the molecular formula ML_2Cl_2 .

Fig. 2

The IR spectra show bands at 3500 cm^{-1} (OH) in all the complexes, suggest that the OH bands of free ligand remain unaltered upon complexation. The bands at 1585 cm^{-1} in 5-substituted-2-dimethylamino-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine assigned to C=N are considerably shifted to lower frequency in complexes **1-6**, which indicate the involvement of nitrogen atom (C=N) in coordination. The bands (C–N stretch) appearing at $1380\text{--}1385\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligands are shifted to lower frequency, suggesting that dimethylamino nitrogen is acting as bridging atom. The C–O bands appearing at $1225, 1265, 1265, 1260\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively in L_1, L_2, L_3 and L_4 are also altered in complexation. The shift of bands in C=N, C–N and C–O to lower frequency indicates the involvement of pyrimidine ring upon complexation.

Further elucidation of the structure of the complexes is obtained from the far IR region. All the metal complexes exhibit two sharp bands in the far IR corresponding to M–Cl and M–N. The bands at $225\text{--}230$ and $240\text{--}285\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to M–Cl and M–N stretches⁶. The bands appear in the region $420\text{--}430\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to M–O, but no such bands are observed in all complexes⁶. All these results confirm the chelation of 5-substituted-2-dimethylamino-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine with metal chloride through dimethylamino nitrogen (C–NMe₂) and nitrogen atom (C=N) in the complexes. The probable structure of the complex is given in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3

Bioassay: The herbicidal activity is screened by dish method. The test plants are barnyardgrass, wheat, jowar, rape, radish and cucumber. The results show that only complexes **3** (100 mg dm^{-3} in DMF) has the control effect that it is up to 81.9% to barnyardgrass and for other complexes the activities are below 50%.

The insecticidal activity of each complex is tested against soybean aphid, armyworm, rice plant hopper and two-spotted spider mite. It is found that only the control effect of **2** (250 mg dm^{-3}) to two-spotted spider mite is 42.4%, while the others are very weakly active.

All of the complexes are tested for antifungal activity against rape sclerotiose and rice bacterial leaf blight. The results of the fungicidal testing show that no significant activity is observed in complexes **1-6**.

Experimental

IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 683 (Perkin-Elmer, U.K.) spectrophotometer and UV spectra on a UV-260 spectrophotometer (Japan). OTA-TG analyses were carried out on a RIGAKU-8150 (Japan) instrument. Microanalyses were done with a Carlo-Erba 1106 elemental analyzer. Molar conductances in DMF were obtained on a DDS-11A (China) instrument.

The ligands were prepared following the methods reported earlier⁷.

The hydrated metal chloride (0.01 mol) in methanol was stirred with the methanolic solution of the ligand (0.02 mol) at RT night over. The resulting solid was washed with methanol and dried under the reduced pressure.

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